

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 DOMAIN INTRODUCTION: DEEP LEARNING

Deep learning (also known as deep structured learning) is part of a broader family of machine learning methods based on artificial neural networks with representation learning. Learning can be supervised, semi-supervised or unsupervised.

Deep-learning architectures such as deep neural networks, deep belief networks, recurrent neural networks and convolutional neural networks have been applied to fields including computer vision, machine vision, speech recognition, natural language processing, audio recognition, social network filtering, machine translation, bioinformatics, drug design, medical image analysis, material inspection and board game programs, where they have produced results comparable to and in some cases surpassing human expert performance.

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) were inspired by information processing and distributed communication nodes in biological systems. ANNs have various differences from biological brains. Specifically, neural networks tend to be static and symbolic, while the biological brain of most living organisms is dynamic (plastic) and analog.

DEEP NEURAL NETWORK

A deep neural network (DNN) is an artificial neural network (ANN) with multiple layers between the input and output layers. There are different types of neural networks but they always consist of the same components: neurons, synapses, weights, biases, and functions. These components functioning similar to the human brains and can be trained like any other ML algorithm.

Deep architectures include many variants of a few basic approaches. Each architecture has found success in specific domains. It is not always possible to compare the performance of multiple architectures, unless they have been evaluated on the same data sets.

DNNs are typically feedforward networks in which data flows from the input layer to the output layer without looping back. At first, the DNN creates a map of virtual neurons and assigns random numerical values, or "weights", to connections between them. The weights and inputs are multiplied and return an output between 0 and 1. If the network did not accurately recognize a particular pattern, an algorithm would adjust the weights. That way the algorithm can make certain parameters more influential, until it determines the correct mathematical manipulation to fully process the data.

1.2 PROJECT DEFINITION:

Diabetic retinopathy is an ailment that occurs in people suffering from diabetes causing progressive damage to the retina, the light-sensitive lining at the back of the eye. Diabetic retinopathy is a serious sight-menacing complication of diabetes. The ability of the body to store and use sugar is intervened by diabetes. The disease is characterized by excess of sugar levels in the blood, which can cause damage throughout the body as well as the eyes. Over a period of time, diabetes can cause damage to the blood vessels in the retina. Diabetic retinopathy is a condition that occurs when blood and other fluids start leaking from these tiny blood vessels causing the retinal tissue to swell. This results in cloudy or blurred vision. This condition usually affects both eyes. The longer a person has diabetes, the more is the probability that they will develop diabetic retinopathy. If left untreated, diabetic retinopathy can lead to blindness. Diabetic people, who experience long periods of high blood sugar, have a tendency of fluid accumulation in the lens which in turn changes the curvature of the lens, leading

to blurred vision. Hence it is recommended that everyone with diabetes must have a comprehensive dilated eye examination once a year. Detecting and treating the ailment at an earlier stage can limit the potential for significant vision loss from diabetic retinopathy.

Diabetic Retinopathy comprises of certain stages which help us to distinguish the severity of the disease and accordingly come up with the prevention methods.

The stages of diabetic retinopathy include:

- No DR: In this stage the eye is not affected with the disease. i.e. eye is healthy.
- Mild DR: In the first stage, mild non proliferative, there will be balloon-like swelling in small areas of the blood vessels in the retina.
- Moderate DR: In the second stage, known as moderate non proliferative retinopathy, some of the blood vessels in the retina will become blocked.
- Severe DR: The third stage, severe non proliferative retinopathy brings with it more blocked blood vessels, which leads to areas of the retina no longer receiving adequate blood flow. Without proper blood flow, the retina can't grow new blood vessels to replace the damaged ones.
- Proliferative DR: The fourth and final stage is known as proliferative retinopathy. This is the advanced stage of the disease. Additional new blood vessels will begin to grow in the retina, but they will be fragile and abnormal. Because of this, they can leak blood which will lead to vision loss and possibly blindness.

Convolutional neural network is a subset of deep learning neural network. It is mainly used for image classification and image analysis. The goal behind CNN is to mimic how human brain analyzes the image. Convolution neural network is comprised of one or more convolutional layers and then followed by one or more fully connected layers.

The CNN consist of input, hidden and output layer. The input layer basically consists of arrays of pixels. The hidden layer is the most important layer as it plays the main role in image computation. Hidden layer comprises of activation functions and biases. The output layer helps us to determine the class score. The benefit of CNN's is that they are easier to train with providing high accuracies.

1.3 PROJECT DESCRIPTION:

Regardless of the type of diabetes, all people recognized with DM want regular and repetitive annual retinal screening for well timed detection and apt treatment of diabetic retinopathy (DR). Conventionally, retinopathy screening is executed by using fundus examination by ophthalmologists or with the help of colour fundus images the use of conventional fundus cameras by trained eye technicians or optometrists. The primary trouble is the grading of the retinal pix by way of ophthalmologists (retinal specialists) or skilled humans, whose numbers are very scarce compared to the burden of patients requiring screening. Second, some of these sufferers are based totally in rural areas and may visit a watch care provider. Till now we have not tested the computer take a look at information, therefore our first goal would be to obtain the identical. Our essential recognition could be to design the sort of detection machine that's especially correct and specific. Our network architecture with dropout strategies yielded full-size category accuracy. This architecture has a few setbacks which includes an additional degree category are needed for the pictures taken from a one-of-a-kind digicam with a specific field of view. Also our network structure is complex and computation extensive requiring excessive stage images processing unit to method the high resolution snap shots wherein the extent of layers stacked greater. We also can put into effect our complete model as a utility on mobile telephones, which will make diabetic retinopathy detection less difficult and time saving.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

Paper 1:

Title: Recent Development on Detection Methods for the Diagnosis of Diabetic Retinopathy

Author Name: Imran Qureshi, Jun Ma

Year: 2019

Explanation:

Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a complication of diabetes that exists throughout the world. DR occurs due to a high ratio of glucose in the blood, which causes alterations in the retinal microvasculature. Without preemptive symptoms of DR, it leads to complete vision loss. However, early screening through computer-assisted diagnosis (CAD) tools and proper treatment have the ability to control the prevalence of DR. Manual inspection of morphological changes in retinal anatomic parts are tedious and challenging tasks. Therefore, many CAD systems were developed in the past to assist ophthalmologists for observing inter- and intra-variations. In this paper, a recent review of state-of-the-art CAD systems for diagnosis of DR is presented. We describe all those CAD systems that have been developed by various computational intelligence and image processing techniques. The limitations and future trends of current CAD systems are also described in detail to help researchers. Moreover, potential CAD systems are also compared in terms of statistical parameters to quantitatively evaluate them. The comparison results indicate that there is still a need for accurate development of CAD systems to assist in the clinical diagnosis of diabetic retinopathy.

Paper 2:

Title: Indian Diabetic Retinopathy Image Dataset (IDRiD): A Database for Diabetic Retinopathy Screening Research

Author Name: Prasanna Porwal , Samiksha Pachade

Year: 2018

Explanation:

Diabetic Retinopathy is the most prevalent cause of avoidable vision impairment, mainly affecting the working-age population in the world. Recent research has given a better understanding of the requirement in clinical eye care practice to identify better and cheaper ways of identification, management, diagnosis and treatment of retinal disease. The importance of diabetic retinopathy screening programs and difficulty in achieving reliable early diagnosis of diabetic retinopathy at a reasonable cost needs attention to develop computer-aided diagnosis tool. Computer-aided disease diagnosis in retinal image analysis could ease mass screening of populations with diabetes mellitus and help clinicians in utilizing their time more efficiently. The recent technological advances in computing power, communication systems, and machine learning techniques provide opportunities to the biomedical engineers and computer scientists to meet the requirements of clinical practice. Diverse and representative retinal image sets are essential for developing and testing digital screening programs and the automated algorithms at their core. To the best of our knowledge, IDRiD (Indian Diabetic Retinopathy Image Dataset), is the first database representative of an Indian population. The dataset provides information on the disease severity of diabetic retinopathy, and diabetic macular edema for each image. This makes it perfect for development and evaluation of image analysis algorithms for early detection of diabetic retinopathy.

Paper 3:

Title: A Brief Review of the Detection of Diabetic Retinopathy in Human Eyes Using Pre-Processing & Segmentation Techniques

Author Name: Yogesh Kumaran, Chandrashekar M. Patil

Year: 2018

Explanation:

In this research article, a brief insight into the detection of DR in human eyes using different types of preprocessing & segmentation techniques is being presented. There are a number of methods of segmenting the blood vessels that are present in the retina & once the retinal nerve fibres are segmented, one can detect whether the eyes are affected with diabetic retinopathy or not. In fact, this detection depends on the area of the RNFL network. If the total area of the nerve fibre is less, then it is affected with diabetic retinopathy (DR)& if the area of the nerve network is more, then the eyes are not affected with the diabetic retinopathy and hence it is normal. It is a well-known fact that diabetes assumes a vital job in the health of the human beings & affects each and every organ. One such organ in the human eye. This DR will give rise to vision loss in the human eye as the optic nerve is connected to the brain.

Paper 4:

Title: Diabetic Retinopathy detection through integration of Deep Learning classification framework

Author Name: Alexander Rakhlin

Year: 2017

Explanation:

This document represents a brief account of ongoing project for Diabetic Retinopathy Detection (DRD) through integration of state-of the art Deep Learning methods. We make use of deep Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), which have proven revolutionary in multiple fields of computer vision including medical imaging, and we bring their power to the diagnosis of eye fundus images. For training our models we used publicly available Kaggle data set. For testing we used portion of Kaggle data withheld from training and Messidor-2 reference standard. Neither withheld Kaggle images, nor Messidor-2 were used for training. For Messidor 2 we achieved sensitivity 99%, specificity 71%, and AUC 0.97. These results close to recent state-of-the-art models trained on much larger data sets and surpass average results of diabetic retinopathy screening when performed by trained optometrists. With continuous development of our Deep Learning models we expect to further increase the accuracy of the method and expand it to cataract and glaucoma diagnostics.

Paper 5:

Title: ADAM: A METHOD FOR STOCHASTIC OPTIMIZATION

Author Name: Diederik P. Kingma, Jimmy Lei Ba

Year: 2017

Explanation:

Adam, an algorithm for first-order gradient-based optimization of stochastic objective functions, based on adaptive estimates of lower-order moments. The method is straightforward to implement, is computationally efficient, has little memory requirements, is invariant to diagonal rescaling of the gradients, and is well suited for problems that are large in terms of data and/or parameters. The method is also appropriate for non-stationary objectives and problems with very noisy and/or sparse gradients. The hyper-parameters have intuitive interpretations and typically require little tuning. Some connections to related algorithms, on which Adam was inspired, are discussed. We also analyze the theoretical convergence properties of the algorithm and provide a regret bound on the convergence rate that is comparable to the best known results under the online convex optimization framework. Empirical results demonstrate that Adam works well in practice and compares favorably to other stochastic optimization methods. Finally, we discuss AdaMax, a variant of Adam based on the infinity norm.

Paper 6:

Title: Convolutional Neural Networks for Diabetic Retinopathy

Author Name: Harry Pratta,_, Frans Coenenb

Year: 2016

Explanation:

The diagnosis of diabetic retinopathy (DR) through colour fundus images requires experienced clinicians to identify the presence and significance of many small features which, along with a complex grading system, makes this a difficult and time consuming task. In this paper, we propose a CNN approach to diagnosing DR from digital fundus images and accurately classifying its severity. We develop a network with CNN architecture and data augmentation which can identify the intricate features involved in the classification task such as micro-aneurysms, exudate and haemorrhages on the retina and consequently provide a diagnosis automatically and without user input. We train this network using a high-end graphics processor unit (GPU) on the publicly available Kaggle dataset and demonstrate impressive results, particularly for a high-level classification task. On the data set of 80,000 images used our proposed CNN achieves a sensitivity of 95% and an accuracy of 75% on 5,000 validation images.

Paper 7:

Title: Batch Normalization: Accelerating Deep Network Training by Reducing Internal Covariate Shift

Author Name: Sergey Ioffe, Christian Szegedy

Year: 2015

Explanation:

Training Deep Neural Networks is complicated by the fact that the distribution of each layer's inputs changes during training, as the parameters of the previous layers change. This slows down the training by requiring lower learning rates and careful parameter initialization, and makes it notoriously hard to train models with saturating nonlinearities. We refer to this phenomenon as internal covariate shift, and address the problem by normalizing layer inputs. Our method draws its strength from making normalization a part of the model architecture and performing the normalization for each training mini-batch. Batch Normalization allows us to use much higher learning rates and be less careful about initialization. It also acts as a regularizer, in some cases eliminating the need for Dropout. Applied to a state-of-the-art image classification model, Batch Normalization achieves the same accuracy with 14 times fewer training steps, and beats the original model by a significant margin. Using an ensemble of batchnormalized networks, we improve upon the best published result on ImageNet classification: reaching 4.9% top-5 validation error (and 4.8% test error), exceeding the accuracy of human raters.

Paper 8:

Title: Diabetic Retinopathy Detection Using Eye Images

Author Name: Mohit Singh Solanki, Dr. Amitabha Mukherjee

Year: 2015

Explanation:

Diabetic Retinopathy is one of the leading causes of blindness and eye disease in working age population of developed world. This project is a attempt towards finding a automated way to detect this disease in its early phase. In this project using supervised learning methods to classify a given set of images into 5 classes. For this task I am employing various image processing techniques and filters to enhance many important features and then using neural for classification. By using 500 images as training input and same number of images for test we got these results on classification In this way we got descent results for our analysis. By table-2 we can see that it gives around 55% accuracy in the results. The code for neural networks took around 6-7 hours to run over the images.

Paper 9:

Title: Prevalence and causes of vision loss in high-income countries and in Eastern and Central Europe in 2015: magnitude, temporal trends and projections

Author Name: Rupert R A Bourne, Jost B Jonas,

Year: 2015

Explanation:

Within a surveillance of the prevalence and causes of vision impairment in high-income regions and Central/Eastern Europe, we update figures through 2015 and forecast expected values in 2020. Based on a systematic review of medical literature, prevalence of blindness, moderate and severe vision impairment (MSVI), mild vision impairment and presbyopia was estimated for 1990, 2010, 2015, and 2020. Age standardised prevalence of blindness and MSVI for all ages decreased from 1990 to 2015 from 0.26% (0.10–0.46) to 0.15% (0.06–0.26) and from 1.74% (0.76–2.94) to 1.27% (0.55–2.17), respectively. In 2015, the number of individuals affected by blindness, MSVI and mild vision impairment ranged from 70 000, 630 000 and 610 000, respectively, in Australasia to 980 000, 7.46 million and 7.25 million, respectively, in North America and 1.16 million, 9.61 million and 9.47 million, respectively, in Western Europe. In 2015, cataract was the most common cause for blindness, followed by age-related macular degeneration (AMD), glaucoma, uncorrected refractive error, diabetic retinopathy and cornea-related disorders, with declining burden from cataract and AMD over time. Uncorrected refractive error was the leading cause of MSVI. New data on burden of presbyopia identify this entity as an important public health problem in this population. Additional research on better treatments, better implementation with existing tools and ongoing surveillance of the problem is needed.

Paper 10:

Title: Rethinking the Inception Architecture for Computer Vision

Author Name: Christian Szegedy, Vincent Vanhoucke

Year: 2015

Explanation:

Convolutional networks are at the core of most state-of-the-art computer vision solutions for a wide variety of tasks. Since 2014 very deep convolutional networks started to become mainstream, yielding substantial gains in various benchmarks. Although increased model size and computational cost tend to translate to immediate quality gains for most tasks (as long as enough labeled data is provided for training), computational efficiency and low parameter count are still enabling factors for various use cases such as mobile vision and big-data scenarios. Here we are exploring ways to scale up networks in ways that aim at utilizing the added computation as efficiently as possible by suitably factorized convolutions and aggressive regularization. We benchmark our methods on the ILSVRC 2012 classification challenge validation set demonstrate substantial gains over the state of the art: 21.2% top-1 and 5.6% top-5 error for single frame evaluation using a network with a computational cost of 5 billion multiply-adds per inference and with using less than 25 million parameters. With an ensemble of 4 models and multi-crop evaluation, we report 3.5% top-5 error and 17.3% top-1 error.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM:

It provides a provision for only manual consultation. Patient has to travel longer distance to consult the doctor. It poses greater risks as the traveling may even make the situation of the patient even more adverse. Patient has to wait for hours for the dilation of eyes so as to widen the pupil. After dilation the doctor has to check for abnormal blood vessels, swelling, retinal detachment, test your vision & cataracts.

In this paper, a new diabetic retinopathy monitoring model is proposed by using the Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization method to improve the image quality and equalize intensities uniformly as the pre-processing step. Then, EfficientNetB5 architecture is used for the classification step. The efficiency of this network is in uniformly scaling all dimensions of the network. The final model is trained once on a mixture of two datasets, Messidor-2 and IDRiD, and evaluated on the Messidor dataset. The area under the curve (AUC) is enhanced from 0.936, which is the highest value in all recent works, to 0.945. Also, once again, to further evaluate the performance of the model, it is trained on a mixture of two datasets, Messidor-2 and Messidor, and evaluated on the IDRiD dataset. In this case, the AUC is enhanced from 0.796, which is the highest value in all recent works, to 0.932. In comparison to other studies, our proposed model improves the AUC.

3.1.1 Disadvantages:

- ✓ While performing training and testing data sets, overfitting occurs.
- ✓ Diabetic Retinopathy is one of the leading causes of blindness and eye disease in working age population of developed world.
- ✓ It is difficult to take the dataset.

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM:

A model is proposed which uses CNN for the automated detection of DR. DR can be classified into several stages such as normal, mild NPDR- small areas of balloon like swellings in the retinal blood vessels, moderate NPDR swelling & distortion of blood vessels, severe NPDR- blood vessels are blocked & causes abnormal growth factor secretion, PDR- growth factors induce proliferation of new blood vessels in the inner retina. Colored fundus images are the input to the CNN model. CNN removes aberrant noise to recognize features like micro-aneurysms & exudates from the fundus images. The model achieves an accuracy of around 95% for a 2 class classification that is the model detects the presence of DR or not & an accuracy of 85% for a 5 class classification that is if DR is present then it's severity is also determined. DR stage classification has been regarded as a critical step in the evaluation & management of DR. Lack of effective treatment can lead to vision impairment or even irreversible blindness. This disease can be diagnosed by examining the fundus images. Deep CNN reduces the complexity of the neural network & so it is widely used in deep learning.

This section is divided in two major parts that is image processing of data and training that neural network with the processed image. The images are taken from Kaggle, where all the images are in one zip file. The images have been further classified in different levels of Diabetic retinopathy for the neural network. Training set of images in the training database is passed to the model for training the CNN model. Here the CNN model used is 2-D CNN sequential model also called keras CNN. A smaller subset, of size 3662 fundus images, of the publicly available EyePacs dataset that is uploaded on Kaggle DR Detection challenge was used for model training and testing. The fundus photographs were cropped from the center snap shots to do away with the black surrounding pixels using Opencv Python. After cropping, the pics have been resized to 300x300. The

neighborhood average was subtracted from each pixel. A sample end result of the photograph preprocessing performed at the fundus pics may be visible. Jupyter IDE was used for picture preprocessing. The convolution layer of CNN will extract features from the source image. The extracted features are down sampled to reduce the dimensionality of the extracted features so as to get more important features by the pooling layer. These features are flattened by the flatten layer into a vector that forms the input to the fully connected layer. Fully connected layer joins all other layers in the model & activation of features is done. This is very essential for the efficiency of stage wise classification.

The first layer is convolutional layer, this layer performs heavy computation which make further job easy. This layer works as an input layer taking $128 \times 128 \times 3$ (i.e. 128 pixels width and height, and 3 because images have depth 3, the color channels) as the input size of the image. Filters of 3×3 matrixes will slide over all the spatial locations. In Max-pooling layer highest weighted feature is extracted, this is achieved by converting above 3×3 matrixes in more compressed matrix. The above 3×3 matrix is the converted into 2×2 matrixes which involves only the highest weighted feature that is present in 3×3 matrixes. Flatten layer converts the matrix of image into one single dimension array which acts as an input to the dense layer. The dropout layer performs inexpensive and powerful operation that highly improve generalization abilities of the neural network. This method involves randomly removing and restoring neurons during the training with a probability determined by the hyperparameters called dropout rate. The fully connected layer has its neurons connected to all neurons in the previous layer. These layers are used as last elements of deep neural classifier, which are feed by the features extracted by the successive convolutional layers. The last layer that produces the output of the network is a softmax layer or sigmoid neuron, depending on the solving task - binary or multiclass classification.

Fig 3.2.1 Layer Activities

Layer Name	Layer Specification	Layer Activation Function
Input Layer	64x64x3	Null
Convolution2D-1	32x(3x3)	ReLU
MaxPooling2D-1	2x2	Null
Convolution2D-2	32x(3x3)	ReLU
MaxPooling2D-1	2x2	Null
Flatten	Null	Null
Dense-1	128 units	ReLU
Dropout-1	20%	Null
Dense-2	128 units	ReLU
Dropout-2	20%	Null
Output	5 units	Softmax

3.2.1 Advantages:

- ✓ Accuracy is high.
- ✓ Execution time is less.
- ✓ In this, there is no overfitting on accuracy.

3.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY:

The feasibility of the project is analysed in this phase and business proposal is put forth with a very general plan for the project and some cost estimates. During system analysis the feasibility study of the proposed system is to be carried out. This is to ensure that the proposed system is not a burden to the company. For feasibility analysis, some understanding of the major requirements for the system is essential.

Three key considerations involved in the feasibility are:

- Economic Feasibility
- Technical Feasibility
- Social Feasibility

3.3.1 ECONOMICAL FEASIBILITY:

This study is carried out to check the economic impact that the system will issue on the organisation. Thus, the developed system as well within the budget and this was achieved because most of the technologies used are freely available. Only the customised products had to be purchased.

3.3.2 TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY:

This study is carried out to check the technical feasibility, that is, the technical requirements of the system. The developed system must have a modest requirement, as only minimal or null changes are required for implementing this system.

3.3.3 SOCIAL FEASIBILITY:

The aspect of study is to check the level of acceptance of system by the user. This includes the process of training the user the system efficiently. The user must not feel threatened system, instead accept it as necessity. His level of confidence must be raised so that he is also able to make some constructive criticism, which is welcomed as he is the final user of the system.

CHAPTER 4

SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE:

System Architecture is a generic discipline to handle objects(existing or to be created) called “systems”, in a way that supports reasoning about the structural properties of these objects Systems Architecture is a response to the conceptual and practical difficulties.

Fig 4.1 System Architecture

4.2 UML DIAGRAMS:

4.2.1 USE CASE DIAGRAM:

A Use Case diagram in the Unified Modelling Language (UML) is a type of behavioural diagram defined by and created from a Use-case analysis. Its purpose is to present a graphical overview of the functionality provided by a system to present in term of actors, their goals and any other dependencies between those use cases.

Fig 4.2.1 UseCase Diagram

4.2.2 SEQUENCE DIAGRAM:

A sequence diagram in the Unified Modelling Language (UML) is a kind of interaction diagram that shows how processes operate with one another in what order. It is a construct of a Message Sequence Chart.

Fig 4.2.2 Sequence Diagram

4.2.3 COLLABORATION DIAGRAM:

Collaboration Diagram are used to visualize the topology of the physical components of a system where the software components are deployed, Collaboration Diagrams are used to describe the static deployment view of a system.

Fig 4.2.3 Collaboration Diagram

4.2.3 ACTIVITY DIAGRAM:

Activity Diagram is a graphical representation of workflow in stepwise activities and actions with support for choice, iteration and concurrency.

Fig 4.2.4 Activity Diagram

4.3 DATAFLOW DIAGRAM:

The data Flow Diagram (DFD) is a graphical representation of the flow of data through an information system. It enables us to represent the processes in your information system from the view point of data.

DFD Level 0:

DFD Level 1:

DFD Level 2:

DFD Level 3:

Fig 4.3 Dataflow Diagram

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

5.1 INTRODUCTION:

The requirements specification is a technical specification of the requirement for the software products. It is the first step in the requirements analysis process it lists the requirements of the particular Software System include functional, performance and security requirements. The purpose of Software requirements specification is to provide a description of the project, its parameters and goals. This describes the project target audience and its user interface, Hardware and Software requirements.

5.2 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS:

- Hard Disk : 500GB and Above
- RAM : 4GB and Above
- Processor : I3 and Above

5.3 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS:

- Operating System : Windows 7 , 8, 10 (64 bit)
- Software : Python , Anaconda Tool
- Language : Python

CHAPTER 6

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

6.1 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION:

Python

- Python is a general-purpose interpreted, interactive, object-oriented, and high-level programming language.
- It was created by Guido van Rossum during 1985- 1990
- Monty Python's Flying Circus”, a BBC comedy series from the 1970s.

Python Applications

- Web Development
- Game Development
- Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence
- Data Science and Data Visualization
- Web Scraping Applications

Python Syntax compared to other programming languages

- Python was designed to for readability, and has some similarities to the English language with influence from mathematics.
- Python uses new lines to complete a command, as opposed to other programming languages which often use semicolons or parentheses.
- Python relies on indentation, using whitespace, to define scope; such as the scope of loops, functions and classes. Other programming languages often use curly-brackets for this purpose.

Python is Interpreted

- In practice, however, for most programs, the difference in execution speed is measured in milliseconds, or seconds at most, and not appreciably noticeable to a human user. The expediency of coding in an interpreted language is typically worth it for most applications.

- For all its syntactical simplicity, Python supports most constructs that would be expected in a very high-level language, including complex dynamic data types, structured and functional programming, and object-oriented programming.
- Python accomplishes what many programming languages don't: the language itself is simply designed, but it is very versatile in terms of what you can accomplish with it.

Technologies used:

Python 3.5.4: Python is an interpreted high-level programming language for general-purpose programming. Created by Guido van Rossum and first released in 1991, Python has a design philosophy that emphasizes code readability, notably using significant whitespace.

Features of anaconda navigator:

Anaconda is a free and open source, easy to install distribution of Python and R programming languages. Anaconda provides a working environment which is used for scientific computing, data science, statistical analysis and machine learning.

The latest distribution of Anaconda is Anaconda 5.3 and is released in October, 2018. It has the conda package, environment manager and a collection of 1000+ open source packages long with free community support.

Anaconda Navigator is a desktop graphical user interface (GUI) included in the Anaconda distribution. It allows us to launch applications provided in the Anaconda distribution and easily manage conda packages, environments and channels without the use of command-line commands. It is available for Windows, macOS and Linux.

Keras library:

Keras is a high-level neural networks API, written in Python and capable of running on top of TensorFlow, CNTK, or Theano. It was developed with a focus on enabling fast experimentation.

Flask library:

Extensions exist for object-relational mappers, form validation, and upload handling, various open authentication technologies and several common framework related tools. Extensions are updated far more regularly than the core Flask program. Flask is commonly used with MongoDB, which gives it more control over databases and history. HTML, CSS and JavaScript:

Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) is the standard markup language for creating web pages and web applications. With Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) and JavaScript, it forms a triad of cornerstone technologies for the World Wide Web. Web browsers receive HTML documents from a web server or from local storage and render the documents into multimedia web pages. HTML describes the structure of a web page semantically and originally included cues for the appearance of the document.

6.2 LIST OF MODULES:

- ✓ Data Collection and Classification
- ✓ Preprocessing
- ✓ Data Preparation
- ✓ CNN Layers
- ✓ Activation Function

6.2 MODULE DESCRIPTION:

6.2.1 DATA COLLECTION AND CLASSIFICATION:

The Kaggle DR Detection mission dataset includes color fundus photographs which can be categorized zero, one, two, three or four for ordinary, slight, mild, extreme and prolific DR, consecutively. We have reduced the DR classification into binary lessons. A smaller subset, of size 3662 fundus images,

of the publicly available EyePacs dataset that is uploaded on Kaggle DR Detection challenge was used for model training and testing.

Fig 6.2.1 Fundus images: (A) Normal (B) Mild (C) Moderate (D) Severe (E) Prolific DR

6.2.2 PREPROCESSING:

The fundus photographs were cropped from the center snap shots to do away with the black surrounding pixels using Opencv Python. After cropping, the pics have been resized to 300x300. The neighborhood average was subtracted from each pixel. A sample end result of the photograph preprocessing performed at the fundus pics may be visible. Jupyter IDE was used for picture preprocessing.

Fig 6.2.2. Original fundus image (Left), cropped and preprocessed fundus image (Right)

6.2.3 DATA PREPARATION:For model training, 2600 images were selected from the normal fundus images dataset for the healthy class, and 330

images were selected from each of the remaining four classes and put in the unhealthy class. For model testing, 732 fundus images were selected from the normal dataset for healthy class and for the unhealthy class.

In training phase, the input of the CNN algorithm will be the preprocessed training data. As the input goes iteratively through each layer (convolutional, pooling, and fully connected), it will identify the features in the images. The layers in the algorithm will find the best features which are needed for classification using feature maps.

The algorithm will first classify whether the patient is suffering from disease or not. If the patient is suffering from the disease, then it will check the severity level of his disease. The output for this will be the patient's severity level.

6.2.4 CNN LAYERS:

CONVOLUTIONAL LAYER

The first layer is convolutional layer, this layer performs heavy computation which make further job easy. This layer works as an input layer taking $128 \times 128 \times 3$ (i.e. 128 pixels width and height, and 3 because images have depth 3, the color channels) as the input size of the image. Filters of 3×3 matrixes will slide over all the spatial locations. The convolutional layer comprises a set of independent filters. Each filter is independently convolved with the image resulting in 32 feature maps.

MAX-POOLING LAYER

In Max-pooling layer highest weighted feature is extracted, this is achieved by converting above 3×3 matrixes in more compressed matrix. The above 3×3 matrix is the converted into 2×2 matrixes which involves only the highest weighted feature that is present in 3×3 matrixes.

FLATTEN LAYER

Flatten layer converts the matrix of image into one single dimension array which acts as an input to the dense layer.

DROPOUT LAYER

The dropout layer performs inexpensive and powerful operation that highly improve generalization abilities of the neural network. This method involves randomly removing and restoring neurons during the training with a probability determined by the hyperparameters called dropout rate.

DENSE LAYER

The fully connected layer has its neurons connected to all neurons in the previous layer. These layers are used as last elements of deep neural classifier, which are feed by the features extracted by the successive convolutional layers.

OUTPUT LAYER

The last layer that produces the output of the network is a softmax layer or sigmoid neuron, depending on the solving task - binary or multiclass classification.

6.2.5 ACTIVATION FUNCTIONS

ReLU:

Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) is the most used activation function in the world right now. Since, it is used in almost all the convolutional neural networks or deep learning.

Fig6.2.5: Neural Network Architecture

As you can see in the above figure, the ReLU is half rectified (from bottom). $f(z)$ is zero when z is less than zero and $f(z)$ is equal to z when z is above or equal to zero.

$$f(x)=x^+=\max(0,x)$$

Fig6.2.5: Graphical representation of ReLU

Softmax:

The softmax function is a more generalized logistic activation function which is used for multiclass classification.

$$\sigma(z)_j = \frac{e^{z_j}}{\sum_{k=1}^K e^{z_k}} \quad \text{for } j=1,\dots,k \text{ and } z=(z_1,\dots,z_k) \in \mathbb{R}^K$$

CHAPTER 7

SYSTEM TESTING

7.1 INTRODUCTION:

Testing is performed to identify errors. It is used for quality assurance. Testing is an integral part of the entire development and maintenance process. The goal of the testing during phase is to verify that the specification has been accurately and completely incorporated into the design, as well as to ensure the correctness of the design itself. Detection of design faults can be achieved by means of inspection as well as walkthrough.

Testing is one of the important steps in the software development phase. Testing checks for the errors, as a whole of the project testing involves the following test cases:

- ✓ Static analysis is used to investigate the structural properties of the Source code.
- ✓ Dynamic testing is used to investigate the behaviour of the source code by executing the program on the test data.

7.2 UNIT TESTING:

Unit testing is conducted to verify the functional performance of each modular component of the software. Unit testing focuses on the smallest unit of the software design (i.e.), the module. The white-box testing techniques were heavily employed for unit testing.

7.3 FUNCTIONAL TESTS:

Functional test cases involved exercising the code with nominal input values for which the expected results are known, as well as boundary values and special values, such as logically related inputs, files of identical elements, and empty files.

Three types of tests in Functional test:

- ✓ Performance Test
- ✓ Stress Test
- ✓ Structure Test

7.3.1 PERFORMANCE TEST:

It determines the amount of execution time spent in various parts of the unit, program throughput, and response time and device utilization by the program unit.

7.3.2 STRESS TEST:

Stress Test is those tests designed to intentionally break the unit. A Great deal can be learned about the strength and limitations of a program by examining the manner in which a programmer in which a program unit breaks.

7.3.3 STRUCTURED TEST:

Structure Tests are concerned with exercising the internal logic of a program and traversing particular execution paths. The way in which White-Box test strategy was employed to ensure that the test cases could Guarantee that all independent paths within a module have been have been exercised at least once.

- ✓ Exercise all logical decisions on their true or false sides.
- ✓ Execute all loops at their boundaries and within their operational bounds.
- ✓ Exercise internal data structures to assure their validity.
- ✓ Checking attributes for their correctness.
- ✓ Handling end of file condition, I/O errors, buffer problems and textual errors in output information.

7.4 INTEGRATION TESTING:

Integration testing is a systematic technique for construction the program structure while at the same time conducting tests to uncover errors associated with interfacing. i.e., integration testing is the complete testing of the set of modules which makes up the product. One approach is to wait until all the units have

passed testing, and then combine them and then tested. This approach is evolved from unstructured testing of small programs. Another strategy is to construct the product in increments of tested units. A small set of modules are integrated together and tested, to which another module is added and tested in combination. And so on. The advantages of this approach are that, interface dispenses can be easily found and corrected.

TESTING TECHNIQUES / TESTING STRATEGIES:

TESTING:

Testing is a process of executing a program with the intent of finding an error. A good test case is one that has a high probability of finding an as-yet – undiscovered error. A successful test is one that uncovers an as-yet- undiscovered error. System testing is the stage of implementation, which is aimed at ensuring that the system works accurately and efficiently as expected before live operation commences. It verifies that the whole set of programs hang together. System testing requires a test consists of several key activities and steps for run program, string, system and is important in adopting a successful new system. This is the last chance to detect and correct errors before the system is installed for user acceptance testing.

7.5 WHITE BOX TESTING:

This testing is also called as Glass box testing. In this testing, by knowing the specific functions that a product has been design to perform test can be conducted that demonstrate each function is fully operational at the same time searching for errors in each function. It is a test case design method that uses the control structure of the procedural design to derive test cases. Basis path testing is a white box testing.

7.6 BLACK BOX TESTING:

The steps involved in black box test case design are:

- ✓ Graph based testing methods

- ✓ Equivalence partitioning
- ✓ Boundary value analysis
- ✓ Comparison testing

7.7 SOFTWARE TESTING STRATEGIES:

A software testing strategy provides a road map for the software developer. Testing is a set activity that can be planned in advance and conducted systematically. Testing begins at the module level and works “outward” toward the integration of the entire computer-based system.

- ✓ Different testing techniques are appropriate at different points in time.
- ✓ The developer of the software and an independent test group conducts testing.
- ✓ Testing and Debugging are different activities but debugging must be accommodated in any testing strategy.

7.7.1 PROGRAM TESTING:

The logical and syntax errors have been pointed out by program testing. A syntax error is an error in a program statement that in violates one or more rules of the language in which it is written. An improperly defined field dimension or omitted keywords are common syntax error. These errors are shown through error messages generated by the computer. A logic error on the other hand deals with the incorrect data fields, out-off-range items and invalid combinations. Since the compilers will not deduct logical error, the programmer must examine the output. Condition testing exercises the logical conditions contained in a module.

7.7.2 SECURITY TESTING :

Security testing attempts to verify the protection mechanisms built in to a system well, in fact, protect it from improper penetration. The system security must be tested for invulnerability from frontal attack must also be tested for invulnerability from rear attack. During security, the tester places the role of individual who desires to penetrate system.

7.7.3 VALIDATION TESTING:

At the culmination of integration testing, software is completely assembled as a package. Interfacing errors have been uncovered and corrected and a final series of software test-validation testing begins. Validation testing can be defined in many ways, but a simple definition is that validation succeeds when the software functions in manner that is reasonably expected by the customer. Software validation is achieved through a series of black box tests that demonstrate conformity with requirement. After validation test has been conducted, one of two conditions exist.

- ✓ The function or performance characteristics confirm to specifications and are accepted.
- ✓ A validation from specification is uncovered and a deficiency created.

7.7.4 USER ACCEPTANCE TESTING:

User acceptance of the system is key factor for the success of any system. The system under consideration is tested for user acceptance by constantly keeping in touch with prospective system and user at the time of developing and making changes whenever required. This is done in regarding to the following points.

- ✓ Input screen design.
- ✓ Output screen design.

CHAPTER 8

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PERFORMANCE PARAMETERS

The parameters that are used to evaluate the performance of the proposed model are accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, false positive rate and precision. If P is the number of positive samples (patient with DR), N is the number of negative samples (patient without DR). True Positive (TP) is the number of patients with DR which is correctly classified. False Positive (FP) is the number of patients without DR which is incorrectly classified. True Negative (TN) is the number of patients without DR which is correctly classified False Negative (FN) is the number of patients with DR which is incorrectly classified. Accuracy = (1) Sensitivity = (2) Specificity = (3) False positive rate = (4) Precision = (5)

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experiment was done on the images obtained from IDRiD online database along with 50 images collected from the regional hospitals in Kerala to form a total of 240 images. After preprocessing, and candidate region extraction, the images were trained with the CNN network which consisted of 10 layers. The training was done on 130 images for 30 epochs. Testing with the trained network resulted in an accuracy of 93.8 percent.

In this section we evaluate the performance and results RCNN techniques. The performance is evaluated by the various performance parameters like accuracy, sensitivity and speed. Input layer takes in a whole color image in CNN and only suspected blocks in R-CNN. While thresholding the intensity of suspected blocks, the range of L component is taken to be greater than 80, a component to be less than -5 and b component to be greater than 70.

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

CONCLUSION:

On success of our project we can quickly detect Diabetic Retinopathy with high accuracy from our trained neural network and our system will help to reduce the damage cause by diabetic retinopathy at early stage. We have created a webapp for the client where the client can use its username and password credentials to login in our system and use dashboard to interact with our system. Our report generation system will give analysis of patient's eye and will help doctors to take quick action .Our system can be further enhanced by training our neural network model on different eye disease so one can get one stop solution for all eye diseases.

FUTURE ENHANCEMENT:

In this proposed system for the objective of detecting and classification of DR as used 214 fundus images from DIARECTDB1. Detected there lesions namely blood vessels, exudates and micro aneurysms from input images. Then extracted necessary features and classified using ANN classifier. The proposed method performed up to classification sensitivity of 95%, precision of 95% and accuracy 96% respectively. The execution time took about 28.064 seconds. As a future work, we can optimize the classifier performance with more images, extracting details features and using different classifier.

APPENDICES

A.SAMPLE CODE

Convolution_Neural_Network:

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import os
print(os.listdir(r"D:\Pro"))
train_df = pd.read_csv(r'D:\Pro\train.csv')
train_df['diagnosis'] = train_df['diagnosis'].astype('str')
train_df['id_code'] = train_df['id_code'].astype(str)+'.png'
from keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
```

```
datagen=ImageDataGenerator(
    rescale=1./255,
    validation_split=0.2,
    shear_range=0.2,
    zoom_range=0.2,
    horizontal_flip=True)
```

```
batch_size = 16
image_size = 96
```

```
train_gen=datagen.flow_from_dataframe(
    dataframe=train_df,
    directory="D:/Pro/train_images",
    x_col="id_code",
    y_col="diagnosis",
    batch_size=batch_size,
    shuffle=True,
    class_mode="categorical",
    target_size=(image_size,image_size),
    subset='training')
```

```
test_gen=datagen.flow_from_dataframe(
    dataframe=train_df,
    directory="D:/Pro/train_images",
    x_col="id_code",
    y_col="diagnosis",
```

```

batch_size=batch_size,
shuffle=True,
class_mode="categorical",
target_size=(image_size,image_size),
subset='validation')
y_train = train_df['diagnosis']
from keras.utils import np_utils
y_train = np_utils.to_categorical(y_train)
num_classes = y_train.shape[1]
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import Dense
from keras.layers import Dropout, GaussianNoise, GaussianDropout
from keras.layers import Flatten, BatchNormalization
from keras.layers.convolutional import Conv2D, SeparableConv2D
from keras.constraints import maxnorm
from keras.layers.convolutional import MaxPooling2D
from keras.utils import np_utils
from keras import backend as K
from keras import regularizers, optimizers

def build_model():
    # create model
    model = Sequential()
    #model.add(Reshape((x_train.shape[0],),))
    #model.add(GaussianDropout(0.3,input_shape=[96,96,3]))
    model.add(Conv2D(15, (3, 3), input_shape=[96,96,3], activation='relu'))
    model.add(GaussianDropout(0.3))
    model.add(Conv2D(30(5,5),activation='relu',kernel_constraint=maxnorm(3)))
    model.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2)))
    model.add(Conv2D(30, (3, 3), activation='relu'))
    model.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2)))
    model.add(Conv2D(50, (5, 5), activation='relu'))
    model.add(Conv2D(50, (7, 7), activation='relu'))
    model.add(Dropout(0.2))
    model.add(Flatten())
    model.add(Dense(256,activation='relu',kernel_regularizer=regularizers.l2(0.01))
)
    model.add(Dense(128, activation='relu'))
    model.add(Dense(128, activation='relu'))
    model.add(Dense(50, activation='relu'))
    model.add(Dense(num_classes,activation='softmax',kernel_regularizer=regularizers.l2(0.0001),activity_regularizer=regularizers.l1(0.01)))

```

```

# Compile model
model.compile(loss='categorical_crossentropy',
optimizer=optimizers.adam(lr=0.0001, amsgrad=True), metrics=['accuracy'])
return model
model = build_model()
from keras.callbacks import EarlyStopping, ModelCheckpoint
es= EarlyStopping(monitor='val_loss', mode ='min', verbose = 1, patience = 20)
mc = ModelCheckpoint('D:/Pro/model.h5', monitor='val_loss', save_best_only =
True, mode ='min', verbose = 1)
model.fit_generator(generator=train_gen,
                    steps_per_epoch=len(train_gen),
                    validation_data=test_gen,
                    validation_steps=len(test_gen),
                    epochs=50,
                    callbacks = [es, mc],
                    use_multiprocessing = True,
                    verbose=1)
from keras.models import load_model
model = load_model('D:/Pro/model.h5')
submission_df = pd.read_csv('../input/sample_submission.csv')
#submission_df['diagnosis'] = submission_df['diagnosis'].astype('str')
submission_df['filename'] = submission_df['id_code'].astype(str)+'.png'
submission_datagen=ImageDataGenerator(rescale=1./255)
submission_gen=submission_datagen.flow_from_dataframe(
    dataframe=submission_df,
    directory="../input/test_images",
    x_col="filename",
    batch_size=batch_size,
    shuffle=False,
    class_mode=None,
    target_size=(image_size,image_size)
)
predictions=model.predict_generator(submission_gen,steps=len(submission_gen))
max_probability = np.argmax(predictions,axis=1)
submission_df.drop(columns=['filename'], inplace= True)
submission_df['diagnosis'] = max_probability
submission_df.to_csv('submission.csv', index=False)

```

Resnet Architecture:

```
import json
```

```

import math
import os
import cv2
from PIL import Image
import numpy as np
from keras import layers
from keras.applications import DenseNet121
from keras.callbacks import Callback, ModelCheckpoint
from keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.optimizers import Adam
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.metrics import cohen_kappa_score, accuracy_score
import scipy
import tensorflow as tf
from tqdm import tqdm

get_ipython().run_line_magic('matplotlib', 'inline')
np.random.seed(2019)
tf.set_random_seed(2019)
train_df = pd.read_csv('D:/Pro/train.csv')
test_df = pd.read_csv('D:/Pro/test.csv')
print(train_df.shape)
print(test_df.shape)
train_df.head()
train_df['diagnosis'].hist()
train_df['diagnosis'].value_counts()

def display_samples(df, columns=4, rows=3):
    fig=plt.figure(figsize=(5*columns, 4*rows))

    for i in range(columns*rows):
        image_path = df.loc[i,'id_code']
        image_id = df.loc[i,'diagnosis']
        img = cv2.imread(f'D:/Pro/train_images/{image_path}.png')
        img = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)

        fig.add_subplot(rows, columns, i+1)
        plt.title(image_id)
        plt.imshow(img)

```

```

plt.tight_layout()
display_samples(train_df)
def get_pad_width(im, new_shape, is_rgb=True):
    pad_diff = new_shape - im.shape[0], new_shape - im.shape[1]
    t, b = math.floor(pad_diff[0]/2), math.ceil(pad_diff[0]/2)
    l, r = math.floor(pad_diff[1]/2), math.ceil(pad_diff[1]/2)
    if is_rgb:
        pad_width = ((t,b), (l,r), (0, 0))
    else:
        pad_width = ((t,b), (l,r))
    return pad_width

def preprocess_image(image_path, desired_size=224):
    im = Image.open(image_path)
    im = im.resize((desired_size, )*2, resample=Image.LANCZOS)

    return im
N = train_df.shape[0]
x_train = np.empty((N, 224, 224, 3), dtype=np.uint8)

for i, image_id in enumerate(tqdm(train_df['id_code'])):
    x_train[i, :, :, :] = preprocess_image(
        f'D:/Pro/train_images/{image_id}.png'
    )
N = test_df.shape[0]
x_test = np.empty((N, 224, 224, 3), dtype=np.uint8)

for i, image_id in enumerate(tqdm(test_df['id_code'])):
    x_test[i, :, :, :] = preprocess_image(
        f'D:/Pro/test_images/{image_id}.png'
    )

y_train = pd.get_dummies(train_df['diagnosis']).values

print(x_train.shape)
print(y_train.shape)
print(x_test.shape)
y_train_multi = np.empty(y_train.shape, dtype=y_train.dtype)
y_train_multi[:, 4] = y_train[:, 4]

for i in range(3, -1, -1):

```

```

y_train_multi[:, i] = np.logical_or(y_train[:, i], y_train_multi[:, i+1])

print("Original y_train:", y_train.sum(axis=0))
print("Multilabel version:", y_train_multi.sum(axis=0))
x_train, x_val, y_train, y_val = train_test_split(
    x_train, y_train_multi,
    test_size=0.15,
    random_state=2019
)

class MixupGenerator():
    def __init__(self, X_train, y_train, batch_size=32, alpha=0.2, shuffle=True,
datagen=None):
        self.X_train = X_train
        self.y_train = y_train
        self.batch_size = batch_size
        self.alpha = alpha
        self.shuffle = shuffle
        self.sample_num = len(X_train)
        self.datagen = datagen

    def __call__(self):
        while True:
            indexes = self.__get_exploration_order()
            itr_num = int(len(indexes) // (self.batch_size * 2))

            for i in range(itr_num):
                batch_ids = indexes[i * self.batch_size * 2:(i + 1) * self.batch_size * 2]
                X, y = self.__data_generation(batch_ids)

                yield X, y

    def __get_exploration_order(self):
        indexes = np.arange(self.sample_num)

        if self.shuffle:
            np.random.shuffle(indexes)

        return indexes

    def __data_generation(self, batch_ids):
        _, h, w, c = self.X_train.shape

```

```

l = np.random.beta(self.alpha, self.alpha, self.batch_size)
X_1 = l.reshape(self.batch_size, 1, 1, 1)
y_1 = l.reshape(self.batch_size, 1)

X1 = self.X_train[batch_ids[:self.batch_size]]
X2 = self.X_train[batch_ids[self.batch_size:]]
X = X1 * X_1 + X2 * (1 - X_1)

if self.datagen:
    for i in range(self.batch_size):
        X[i] = self.datagen.random_transform(X[i])
        X[i] = self.datagen.standardize(X[i])

if isinstance(self.y_train, list):
    y = []

    for y_train_ in self.y_train:
        y1 = y_train_[batch_ids[:self.batch_size]]
        y2 = y_train_[batch_ids[self.batch_size:]]
        y.append(y1 * y_1 + y2 * (1 - y_1))
    else:
        y1 = self.y_train[batch_ids[:self.batch_size]]
        y2 = self.y_train[batch_ids[self.batch_size:]]
        y = y1 * y_1 + y2 * (1 - y_1)

return X, y

```

BATCH_SIZE = 32

```

def create_datagen():
    return ImageDataGenerator(
        zoom_range=0.15, # set range for random zoom
        # set mode for filling points outside the input boundaries
        fill_mode='constant',
        cval=0., # value used for fill_mode = "constant"
        horizontal_flip=True, # randomly flip images
        vertical_flip=True, # randomly flip images
    )

# Using original generator
data_generator = create_datagen().flow(x_train, y_train,
batch_size=BATCH_SIZE, seed=2019)
# Using Mixup

```

```

mixup_generator = MixupGenerator(x_train, y_train,
batch_size=BATCH_SIZE, alpha=0.2, datagen=create_datagen())()
]
true_labels = np.array([1, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1])
pred_labels = np.array([1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1])

accuracy_score(true_labels, pred_labels)

cohen_kappa_score(true_labels, pred_labels)

class Metrics(Callback):
    def on_train_begin(self, logs={}):
        self.val_kappas = []

    def on_epoch_end(self, epoch, logs={}):
        X_val, y_val = self.validation_data[:2]
        y_val = y_val.sum(axis=1) - 1

        y_pred = self.model.predict(X_val) > 0.5
        y_pred = y_pred.astype(int).sum(axis=1) - 1

        _val_kappa = cohen_kappa_score(
            y_val,
            y_pred,
            weights='quadratic'
        )

        self.val_kappas.append(_val_kappa)

        print(f"val_kappa: {_val_kappa:.4f}")

        if _val_kappa == max(self.val_kappas):
            print("Validation Kappa has improved. Saving model.")
            self.model.save('model.h5')

    return

densenet = DenseNet121(
    weights='C:/Users/user/Downloads/DenseNet-BC-121-32-no-top.h5',
    include_top=False,
    input_shape=(224,224,3)
)

```

```

def build_model():
    model = Sequential()
    model.add(densenet)
    model.add(layers.GlobalAveragePooling2D())
    model.add(layers.Dropout(0.5))
    model.add(layers.Dense(5, activation='sigmoid'))

    model.compile(
        loss='binary_crossentropy',
        optimizer=Adam(lr=0.00005),
        metrics=['accuracy']
    )

    return model
model = build_model()
model.summary()
# In[24]:
kappa_metrics = Metrics()

history = model.fit_generator(
    data_generator,
    steps_per_epoch=x_train.shape[0] / BATCH_SIZE,
    epochs=15,
    validation_data=(x_val, y_val),
    callbacks=[kappa_metrics]
)
with open('history.json', 'w') as f:
    json.dump(history.history, f)

history_df = pd.DataFrame(history.history)
history_df[['loss', 'val_loss']].plot()
history_df[['acc', 'val_acc']].plot()

```

Web:

```

from flask import *
app = Flask(__name__)
import tensorflow as tf, sys
import tensorflow.compat.v1 as tf
tf.disable_v2_behavior()

```

```

import os
import sqlite3 as sql
import base64
from flask import Flask ,render_template,request,jsonify,session
from flask import Flask,abort,render_template,request,redirect,url_for
#from werkzeug import secure_filename
#Flask Libraries
from flask import Flask, redirect, url_for, render_template, request
import requests
import urllib
@app.route('/', methods=['GET', 'POST'])
def home():
    return render_template('index.html')

def validate(username,password):
    con = sql.connect('static/chat.db')
    completion = False
    with con:
        cur = con.cursor()
        cur.execute('SELECT * FROM persons')
        rows = cur.fetchall()
        for row in rows:
            dbuser = row[1]
            dbpass = row[2]
            if dbuser == username:
                completion = (dbpass == password)
    return completion

@app.route('/login', methods=['GET', 'POST'])
def login():
    error = None
    if request.method == 'POST':
        username = request.form['username']
        password = request.form['password']
        completion = validate(username,password)
        if completion == False:
            error = 'invalid Credentials. please try again.'
        else:
            session['username'] = request.form['username']
            return render_template('file_upload_form.html')
    return render_template('file_upload_form.html', error=error)

```

```

@app.route('/register', methods = ['GET','POST'])
def register():
    if request.method == 'POST':
        try:
            name = request.form['name']
            username = request.form['username']
            password = request.form['password']
            with sql.connect("static/chat.db") as con:
                cur = con.cursor()
                cur.execute("INSERT INTO persons(name,username,password)
VALUES (?,?,"),(name,username,password))
                con.commit()
                msg = "Record successfully added"
            except:
                con.rollback()
                msg = "error in insert operation"
            finally:
                return render_template("index.html",msg = msg)
                con.close()
        return render_template('register.html')

```

```

@app.route('/list')
def list():
    con = sql.connect("static/chat.db")
    con.row_factory = sql.Row

    cur = con.cursor()
    cur.execute("select * from persons")

    rows = cur.fetchall();
    return render_template("list.html",rows = rows)

```

```

@app.route('/upload')
def upload():
    return render_template("file_upload_form.html")

```

```

@app.route('/success', methods = ['POST'])
def success():
    if request.method == 'POST':
        f = request.files['file']

```

```

# change this as you see fit
#image_path = sys.argv[1]
image_path =f.filename
# Read in the image_data
image_data
tf.gfile.FastGFile("D:/Automated_Diabetic_Retinopathy_web/dataset/"+str(image_path), 'rb').read()

# Loads label file, strips off carriage return
label_lines = [line.rstrip() for line
                in tf.gfile.GFile("models/retrained_labels.txt")]

# Unpersists graph from file
with tf.gfile.FastGFile("models/retrained_graph.pb", 'rb') as f:
    graph_def = tf.GraphDef()
    graph_def.ParseFromString(f.read())
    _ = tf.import_graph_def(graph_def, name='')

with tf.Session() as sess:
    # Feed the image_data as input to the graph and get first prediction
    softmax_tensor = sess.graph.get_tensor_by_name('final_result:0')

    predictions = sess.run(softmax_tensor,
                           {'DecodeJpeg/contents:0': image_data})

    # Sort to show labels of first prediction in order of confidence
    top_k = predictions[0].argsort()[-len(predictions[0]):][::-1]
    print(top_k)
    m=[]
    for node_id in top_k:
        human_string = label_lines[node_id]
        score = predictions[0][node_id]
        for j in human_string,score:
            print(j)
            m.append(j)

        #print('%s (score = %.5f)' % (human_string, score))

    return render_template("success.html", list2 = m)

if __name__ == '__main__':
    app.run(debug = True)

```

B. SCREENSHOTS:

Data Collection:

Fig 3 Fundus images: (A) Normal (B) Mild (C) Moderate (D) Severe (E) Prolific DR

Preprocessing:

Fig 4. Original fundus image (Left), cropped and preprocessed fundus image (Right)

Training Set:

Testing Set:

Dashboard:

Test case:

Prediction:

success

127.0.0.1:5000/success

Diabetic Retinopathy Detection

File uploaded successfully

percentage_of_diabetic_retinopathy
0.90488577

percentage_of_nondiabetic_retinopathy
0.09511419

A collection of medical equipment including a stethoscope, a thermometer, a pill bottle, and a tablet displaying a doctor in a white coat. The background is a light blue gradient.

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